

Reliable Messaging for Tactical Group Communication

Brian Adamson and Joseph P. Macker
U.S. Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, D.C. 20375

Abstract - Command and Control and other applications operating in tactical edge networks often require group-wise communication to effectively support military operations. Tactical users rely upon group situational awareness. Mission planning and execution involves distributing force orders and supporting information among collaborating groups. Network-centric concepts of operation offer the promise of a more flexible and responsive fighting force if the necessary information can be effectively disseminated and exchanged among warfighting users and elements. The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has conducted research and development of reliable multicast transport protocols for over a decade. The NACK-Oriented Reliable Multicast (NORM) protocol specification provides robust reliable transport and ancillary functions to support different application needs. The NRL NORM "toolkit" implementation provides controls for application developers to develop robust and efficient group messaging applications capable of operating in tactical edge network environments. This paper describes these mechanisms and presents some results from laboratory and field experiments.

Introduction

Messaging among groups and communities of interest is an important facet of effective military operation, particularly as information superiority has been increasingly recognized as a critical force multiplier. Tactical edge systems that assert and respond to maneuver control, perform mission planning and execution, and assimilate and disseminate Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) data benefit greatly when information can be shared on a group-wise basis. Many of these tactical edge systems rely upon wireless communications that are limited in throughput and often provide challenging latency and bit error rate (BER) characteristics. One benefit is that the typical broadcast nature of radio communication can naturally support group communication in an efficient manner.

However, group communication, as compared to point-to-point communication is more complex with respect to reliable transfer of information. With point-to-point communication between two end points, the thread of communication is immediately suspended when connectivity fails or one of the end points stops participating. This is contrasted to group communication where it is possible for the thread of communication to actually transcend the original participants if new group members join over time while others leave. And different applications will have different policies for

maintaining ongoing communication in absence of some participants.

There are multiple aspects of maintaining consistent and reliable exchange of information among groups of participants in dynamic settings that typify tactical edge networks. At a basic level where some consistent degree of communication connectivity can be maintained among the group members, there are numerous challenges providing robust and efficient information transfer. At a level beyond, additional mechanisms are needed to maintain persistence when extreme disruption to communication connectivity or where networks may fragment and coalesce over time. Some group communication transfer needs also have different tradeoffs in the competing constraints of delay versus reliability.

This paper addresses some network data transport mechanisms suitable for the tactical edge environment where the network topology maintains a reasonable degree of connectivity (although perhaps throughput-limited and lossy) among group members with respect to the duration of information transfer. While this work does not fully address the needs for long-term persistence in highly disruptive networks, the protocols described here can provide a basis for additional mechanisms to build upon.

In addition to simply providing robust and efficient reliable data delivery, candidate protocols should also possess other characteristics necessary to conduct an ongoing dialog in support of group communication in a dynamic environment. For example, reestablishment of connections or state to support reliable data transfer should not be overly burdensome as connectivity performance and characteristics change or momentary disruptions occur. Similarly, different group messaging applications may have significantly different requirements for data framing and delivery constraints and the protocol mechanisms identified must be able to support a broad set of paradigms in a wide range of network conditions. It would be desirable for such protocols to be tunable with respect to meeting application utility goals but be self-managing with respect to adapting to different networks.

The Information Technology Division of NRL has developed reliable network transport mechanisms beginning with its Multicast Dissemination Protocol (MDP) work [1] and leading to the NACK-Oriented Reliable Multicast (NORM) that has been standardized within the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [2]. The focus of MDP was specifically for bulk content delivery but was successfully adapted for group messaging in the U.S. Army Force Battle Command Brigade and Below (FBCB2) system. The NORM protocol provides the same capabilities as MDP but also supplements its design with a number of features for more effective group-wise messaging and to support a more general set of applications.

NORM Protocol Overview

The NACK-Oriented Reliable Multicast (NORM) protocol is a general-purpose reliable network data transport protocol that is described in Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) Request For Comments (RFC) 5740. The Naval Research Laboratory maintains a freely-available, reference implementation of the NORM protocol, including the enhancements described here, at <http://cs.itd.nrl.navy.mil/work/norm>[3]. NORM provides end-to-end reliable transport for application data using selective Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ) with Negative-Acknowledgments from the recipient(s) used to initiate repair transmissions from the sender(s). Additionally, NORM uses dynamic, adaptive timers to scale its operation to different network conditions and maintain efficient and robust data delivery even as conditions change. The term “repair transmissions” is used purposefully here as NORM can also reactively use parity-based, erasure-filling Forward Error Correction (FEC) coding *packets* instead of classical packet retransmission of original packets for enhanced multicast scaling properties [4] in response to repair requests (i.e. NACKs). Additionally, the packet-based FEC content can be proactively multiplexed into the original packet stream for some degree of reliability and robustness without any feedback from the receiver(s). Furthermore, hybrid proactive/reactive FEC operation can be configured to make tradeoffs in reliable data delivery latency and overhead for specific application needs or network connection types [5]. While the name of NORM implies multicast operation, the protocol is also well-suited for unicast (point-to-point) information transfer. This paper focuses on the capabilities of NORM that provide a rich set of mechanisms to support group-wise communication in challenging network environments.

Table 1 lists the five principal NORM protocol message types. The first three listed are considered “sender” messages and the remaining two are “receiver” messages.

Message Type	Purpose
NORM_DATA	Application data and FEC content
NORM_INFO	Application transport object meta-data
NORM_CMD	Sender protocol control and signaling
NORM_NACK	Receiver requests for repair content
NORM_ACK	Receiver acknowledgements

Table 1 - NORM Protocol Message Types

Unlike some other transport protocols, the NORM design separates the functions of reliability, congestion control, and flow control into distinct mechanisms. The bulk of the NORM Protocol Specification addresses reliability mechanisms based upon packet-level FEC concepts and specifies congestion control operation that is compatible with the ubiquitous Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). However, the congestion control mechanism is supported using header extensions to the NORM protocol messages and alternative schemes to meet different application or network

environment needs can be specified and implemented, including fixed-rate operation. In addition to reliable transport, the protocol specification describes some control messages termed NORM “commands” that are used for some pre-defined protocol functions such as round-trip timing estimation, congestion control feedback collection, and optional positive-acknowledgement collection. The NORM “command” set is also extensible with support for application-defined functions and has built-in support for protocol message types that can be used to facilitate end-to-end flow control in a scalable and efficient manner.

The NORM_DATA messages are used by senders to convey application content (and FEC encoded repair packets for that content reactively, as needed, and/or proactively, as pre-configured) while NORM_NACK messages are generated by receivers to selectively request repair of missing content. This basic mechanism comprises the NORM reliability mechanism. The NORM_INFO message is an optional supplemental message a sender can use to provide out-of-band “meta-data” for an application data unit (i.e., transport object). The NORM_INFO content is limited to a single packet payload and is an “atomic” unit that can be quickly requested and provided outside of the scope of the more stateful FEC-based reliable content delivery process.

The NORM_CMD messages have a number of sub-types and are used in various aspects of NORM operation. Examples include collection of feedback from the receiver(s) to measure round-trip timing and congestion control for adapting protocol operation to changing network conditions. The NORM_ACK message is available (when a NACK is not needed) to respond to some of these “command” messages. Note that when NACKs are generated, protocol control feedback is also opportunistically “piggy-backed” with the repair request content. The protocol specification also allows for a range of “application-defined” NORM_CMD sub-types that can be used for specific purposes. The NORM_CMD message variants and their uses separate from NORM_DATA transmission allow congestion control, flow control, and other protocol operations to be distinct from reliability and allow the protocol to fulfill some of the complex needs of group communication.

The performance of the packet-level, FEC-based reliability mechanisms has been investigated and described in other work in the context of delivery of “bulk” content [4]. The gains of packet-level FEC are most evident for such “bulk” content and multicast operation. However, this paper focuses on several aspects, in addition to the reliability mechanisms, of the NORM protocol design that allow it to be useful for group-wise messaging. In particular, the NORM protocol supports form of “stream” delivery where a stream is managed as bulk content object, but of no predefined size. Additionally, the NORM “stream” mode of transport defined has mechanisms that allow late receiver entry and automated session recovery after network outages with identification of any application-defined stream message boundaries.

Protocol Mechanisms

In the NORM protocol, the usually intertwined elements of reliability, congestion control, and flow control provided by end-to-end transport protocols are distinct separable, and somewhat independent components. In fact, due to the building block approach [6] of the protocol design, those elements, in some cases, are even “pluggable” (i.e. replaceable) via supported header-extension features of the protocol specification. For example, the FEC encoding types are dynamic and extensible [7] and even some protocol functions, like congestion control operation, can be extended in variants of the NORM specification.

Packet-Level FEC and Reliability

NORM uses packet erasure coding which is a form of what is sometimes now termed intra-session network coding [8]. As mentioned previously, the NORM can be configured to apply the packet erasure coding proactively, as an added component of data transmission and/or reactively, as a response to NACK repair requests from the receiver(s). The use of FEC for reactive repair transmissions allows NORM to scale to large multicast group sizes and maintain effective reliable delivery and even offers immediate performance benefits for even small multicast groups. The option to proactively embed FEC packets as part of the transmission allows some measure of reliability for unidirectional network communication. Additionally, its use may reduce the reliable data delivery latency for operation on long delay channels. The trade-off between these two operating regions is dependent upon the application needs and the expected network environment. However, NORM allows for the hybrid form of proactive and reactive FEC packet transmission that enables a continuum of operating points.

NORM provides encoding and reliability mechanisms to support different transport modes. For bulk content delivery, the data “object” is logically portioned into coding blocks of packet-sized “segments” where each segment serves as a source symbol for FEC coding. Streamed content (e.g., multimedia voice, video, chat and other sources) coding blocks are constructed “on-the-fly” as data is provided to the stream. When the stream is composed of a series of small messages, the coding is thus applied across multiple messages to efficiently realize coding gain for reliable delivery and/or repair of the stream. NORM supports reliable, in-order delivery of streamed content. Since the NACK-based, selective ARQ reliability mechanism of NORM is somewhat separate of its rate control, it is possible to leverage the proactive FEC and ARQ features to provide “quasi-reliable” delivery of real-time content within a fixed latency bound. This has been successfully applied for robust network video streaming and voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) applications.

Congestion Control

Congestion control is a critical aspect of end-to-end transport protocol operation. A key feature of network systems is the ability to allow applications shared access to communication resources with little or no pre-coordination. End-to-end congestion control can allow networks to scale and adapt with minimal complexity required from intermediate systems (e.g. routers, etc).

The current NORM specification describes a “TCP-Friendly” rate control procedure (NORM-CC) based upon the TCP-Friendly Multicast Congestion Control specification [9] that has been shown to co-exist well with TCP flows and work for multicast data flows [10][11]. While the NORM protocol and even the specified rate control algorithm have attributes well-suited for the often wireless environments needed for tactical systems, the TCP-Friendly aspect of its design leads to some of the same limitations of TCP in wireless systems. Most notable is the negative effect of packet loss due to bit errors or contention that often occur in wireless systems. Both TCP and the TCP-Friendly NORM-CC assume packet loss is due to buffer overflows of congestion and backoff their transmission rate. However, with NORM, its rate control is a separate, “pluggable” component that can be replaced with an alternative algorithm and support protocol header extensions.

Recently, the authors have developed and evaluated a congestion control mechanism for NORM that uses Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN) markings that can be provided by routers as a principal means of sensing when congestion is occurring. This technique is referred to here as NORM-CCE. Initial evaluations have shown this technique is robust against packet loss due to bit error rate (BER) and the congestion avoidance aspects of NORM receiver feedback collection mitigate pathological behavior when network outage or receiver failure occurs. Figure 1 provides an overview of the congestion control performance of TCP, NORM-CC, and the newly developed NORM-CCE. The “UDP” case is simply unreliable, best effort datagram delivery, but represents the maximum goodput that could be achieved for the packet size used.

Figure 1 –Congestion Control Performance in Lossy Links

For these experiments, a topology approximating that have a “bent pipe” satellite communication system was modeled and the BER of the satellite link was varied across a range of values. TCP and NORM-CC both exhibit decreasing ability to make good utilization of network resources as BER and, hence, packet loss increase. However, NORM-CCE is able to maintain good utilization up until the point of very high packet loss (approximately 40%). It is expected that additional improvements to utilization at low BER can be achieved for NORM-CCE with further refinement of the Random Early Detection (RED) and ECN packet marking parameters and the NORM response to ECN. For the initial trials conducted here, a relatively default set of parameters were set for the RED/ECN queuing process [12]. The exception was that RED “early dropping” of packets was disabled (i.e., ECN marking only) and any dropping determined by router queue limits. The early results shown in Figure 1 are promising. Further investigation of this technique is underway.

It should be noted these current congestion and rate control techniques tend to apply towards more longer-term, steady-state transmission of content. However, many messaging applications may exhibit highly bursty and/or low duty cycle activity. The authors’ reference NORM protocol implementation provides additional controls for bounding the rate adjustment to meet required application utility. This implies more deterministic allocation and control of network system resources.

Flow Control

In TCP, flow control is a natural by-product of the protocol’s acknowledgement based reliability and congestion control operation. For a NACK-based protocol, flow control is a more separate consideration. The authors’ NORM implementation provides multiple mechanisms that allow a range of more or less flow control to be asserted in conjunction with reliable transfer. The flow control options include:

- 1) Explicit “watermark” positive acknowledgement (ACK)
- 2) Implicit “watermark” achievement based on a lack of negative acknowledgement (NACK) repair requests from the receiver set.
- 3) A soft, timer-based flow control that holds enqueued transmit data and limits “repair window” advancement based on group round-trip timing (GRTT) and NACK activity.
- 4) A purposeful disabling of any flow control to allow the application to “push” transmission forward with newly enqueued data (e.g., for real-time message streams)

The first, most explicit option is the separate positive acknowledgement feature that is part of the NORM protocol specification. Invocation of this feature allows the sender to request positive acknowledgment of reaching a “watermark” point in the ongoing transmission from a specific set of receivers. This can be applied for unicast or modest multicast group sizes and even for larger group sizes if latency is not a

significant concern. The “watermark” acknowledgement request can be multiplexed with ongoing data transmission so that “dead air” time can be avoided if desired. As mentioned, this provides the most explicit and assured form of flow control if the application uses successful “watermark” acknowledgement as a cue to move forward in sending additional new data and advancing its “repair window”.

The second and third options are less explicit and similar in that the NORM sender’s knowledge of GRTT and current NACK activity is used to regulate flow control. The second, implicit “watermark” approach makes use of the NORM_CMD(FLUSH) signaling to warn the receiver set to NACK for any repair needs through the indicated “watermark” and waits until this flushing has fully completed with no NACK activity before declaring the “watermark” completed. The third option simply sets a minimum time limit that is adapted to the sender-estimated GRTT for which transmitted data must be buffered without NACK activity before the application can enqueue new, overriding data, thus advancing the effective “repair window”.

Finally, the fourth option represents a complete disabling of flow control allowing the application to enqueue new data without regards to whether prior transmissions were reliably transferred. This feature is useful for real-time message flows where new data subsumes the data that was previously enqueued. A specific sender transmission cache or stream buffer size is set in the NORM implementation to bound the repair window and hence the maximum latency due to reliable delivery. An application can control this behavior to makes its own trade-off of latency and reliability to best meet its data delivery needs.

Session Control

The current NORM specification defines operation using User Datagram Protocol (UDP) for delivery of NORM protocol messages. Senders and receivers require a priori knowledge of address and port numbers used for communication. NORM is not really completely “connectionless” since the sender and receivers maintain state to achieve reliable transfer, but is somewhat “connection-free” in that an explicit connection setup is not required to initiate reliable reception as in the case of fully connection-oriented protocols like TCP. This property allows receivers to begin reliable reception of streams of content already in progress or to rapidly resume reception after a network outage without any explicit connection establishment signaling.

It is expected that session control protocols may be specified as part of application design to “boot strap” group communication. The NORM protocol has features that can be used to support such application session control. For example, the NORM_CMD message type supports a range of “application-defined” commands that can be used for application-specific purposes. The use of these commands is more atomic and requires less state and complexity than reliable data delivery. Thus, the use of these commands scales well for potentially large group session coordination and control while benefiting from underlying NORM transmission rate control and GRTT knowledge. A similar range of NORM_CMD sub-types is also reserved for future specification so that standardized session control protocols might be realized using the NORM framework.

Messaging Support

Connection-oriented TCP flows assume the receiver application understands the context of the data written to the connection by the sender and benefits from the full, in-order reliable delivery of that content. Thus a simple byte stream service is provided. Other protocols (e.g. SCTP) have begun to provide mechanisms for applications to convey message boundaries and multiplex messages across the provided transport connection. The often loose coordination of multicast application operation dictated that the NORM protocol allow for late-joining receivers to start receiving content even when the session was already in progress. In this spirit, the NORM protocol provides a means for applications providing stream delivery to “mark” application message boundaries so that receivers can rapidly join a stream “in progress” and begin reliable reception of message content. And, when a network outage or other temporary system failure occurs, a receiver can rejoin and/or resume reliable reception of ongoing message content.

NORM provides for segmentation and reassembly of even large application message content. Additionally, the NORM reference implementation allows message streams to be intelligently “flushed” to force transmission of new content irrespective of usual segmentation or FEC encoding considerations. This feature is analogous to the “no delay” option of TCP sockets that is often used for more interactive applications (e.g. telnet, secure shell (*ssh*), chat, etc).

Wireless Network Performance

Reliable data transport in multihop wireless networks is often problematic due to the combination of BER-related packet loss and/or contention behaviors of multiple access protocols. These issues have been explored for TCP and similar protocols in other work [13]. Because of its various properties, NORM demonstrates robust performance in wireless networks when operating at predetermined fixed data rates [14]. A common pathological case that has been examined is a “string” of nodes that comprise a multihop path from a source to a destination. We conducted simulation studies to compare the performance of the robust selective

ARQ of NORM coupled with the NORM-CCE and TCP in this classic scenario. For the results illustrated in Figure 2, an high-fidelity 802.11 model (the “dei80211mr “multirate”) was configured in the ns-2 simulation tool with the default unicast MAC-layer hop-by-hop retransmissions enabled. A point-to-point data flow was transmitted from a source to a destination with the “hop count” from the source to destination increased with successive trials.

Figure 2 - Multihop Wireless Performance (with MAC-layer retransmissions)

The “UDP” data series in Figure 2 represents the maximum achievable throughput but provides only unreliable, best effort delivery. As the “hop count” is increased this throughput diminishes due to contention including interference of transmissions outside of communication range. The MAC-layer retransmissions mitigate non-congestion packet loss and thus TCP, NORM-CC, and NORM-CCE offer similar performance.

The results in Figure 3 represent the same scenario, but with the 802.11 MAC-layer retransmission disabled. The 300 meter separation of the nodes results in a small amount of packet loss due to BER. As a result, the NORM-CC rate control approach also suffers and exhibits degradation with hop count increase similar to TCP. Note that the BER-induced loss limits TCP performance even for a single hop. The added packet loss also reduces the goodput achieved in the NORM-CCE case, although it is not impacted much as compared to TCP or the NORM-CC case. Additionally, although not shown here, there is an increase in the latency of end-to-end reliable delivery without the MAC-layer retransmission capability.

Figure 3 - Multihop Wireless Performance (no MAC-layer retransmissions)

While the performance of NORM-CCE for point-to-point wireless links and multihop wireless networks has value, it is not a panacea solution for wireless network congestion control. As an end-to-end protocol operating strictly at Layer 4, it can suffer from the “flow-in-the-middle” problem [15] and other pathologies of Layer 2 wireless contention. Further study should be conducted to assess the compatibility of NORM’s end-to-end mechanisms with potential solutions to these issues such as DiffQ [15] or other similar cross-layer concepts.

Summary

The NORM protocol specification and reference implementation supports a variety of mechanisms and features to support reliable, efficient delivery of messaging and other data content for tactical edge network applications. The separable aspects of NORM with respect to reliability, flow control, congestion control and other features allow the protocol to be adapted to meet a wide range of application utility. NORM specifically provides a suite of capabilities to support the semantics of group communication. However, its robust performance and behaviors that are well-suited for the wireless environment also have value for unicast network communications where protocols like TCP may not perform well or provide extended features (e.g. quasi-reliable, real-time delivery) needed for tactical information exchange. While there is immediate applicability for NORM in numerous tactical network systems, further work needs to be conducted to explore the tradeoffs and considerations among end-to-end reliable data delivery and emerging cross-layer concepts for wireless networks.

References

- [1] Macker J.P., R.B. Adamson, "The Multicast Dissemination Protocol Toolkit," Proc. IEEE Military Communications Conference (MILCOM) 99, November 1999.
- [2] Adamson B., C. Bormann, M. Handley, J. Macker, "NACK-Oriented Reliable Multicast (NORM) Transport Protocol", Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) RFC 5740, November 2009.
- [3] Adamson, B., "NORM Software Source Code and Documentation", <http://cs.itd.nrl.navy.mil/work/norm>.
- [4] Macker J.P., "Reliable Multicast Transport and Integrated Erasure-based Forward Error Correction," Proc. IEEE Military Communications Conference (MILCOM) 1997, October 1997.
- [5] Gossink D, J.P. Macker, "Reliable Multicast and Integrated Parity Retransmission with Channel Estimation," IEEE GLOBECOM, 1998.
- [6] Whetten, B. Vicisano, L. Kermode, R., Handley, M., Floyd, S., and M. Luby, "Reliable Multicast Transport Building Blocks for One-to-Many Bulk Data Transfer", Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) RFC 3048, January 2001.
- [7] Watson, M., M. Luby, and L. Vicisano, "Forward Error Correction (FEC) Building Block", IETF RFC 5052, August 2007.
- [8] Tracey Ho, Harish Viswanathan, Dynamic algorithms for multicast with intra-session network coding, IEEE Transactions on Information Theory, v.55 n.2, p.797-815, February 2009
- [9] Widmer, J., and M. Handley, "TCP-Friendly Multicast Congestion Control (TFMCC) Protocol Specification, IETF RFC 4654, August 2006.
- [10] Macker J.P., R. Brian Adamson, "A TCP Friendly, Rate-Based Mechanism for NACK-Oriented Reliable Multicast Congestion Control," in IEEE GLOBECOM 2001.
- [11] Widmer, J., and M. Handley, "Extending Equation-Based Congestion Control to Multicast Applications", ACM SIGCOMM, August 2001.
- [12] S. Floyd, RED: Discussion of Setting Parameters, Nov 1997, <http://www.aciri.org/floyd/REDparameters.txt>.
- [13] Z Fu, P Zerfos, H Luo, S Lu, L Zhang, M Gerla, "The Impact of Multihop Wireless Channel on TCP Throughput and Loss", IEEE GLOBECOM 2003.
- [14] C. Rigano, K. Scott, J. Bush, R. Edell, S. Parikh, R. Wade and B. Adamson, Mitigating Naval Network Instabilities with Disruption Tolerant Networking, MILCOM 2008, San Diego, CA, November 2008.
- [15] A. Warriar, S. Janakiraman, P. Wason, S. Ha and I. Rhee, DiffQ: Differential Backlog Congestion Control for Multi-hop Wireless Networks, INFOCOM 2009.